

A STUDY ON THE METAL COMPLEXES OF ETHYLENEDIAMINE TETRA-ACETIC ACID

BY RABINDRA LAL DUTTA AND PRIYADARANJAN RAY

Ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA), usually a hexadentate ligand, can also function as a pentadentate one, has been established through the isolation of the mono-hydroxo-EDTA complexes of trivalent chromium and trivalent iron, in the form of their copper and nickel bisbiguanidinium salts. The chromium complex was precipitated at pH 7.6–7.8 and the iron complex at pH 8.8. Besides these, copper, nickel and manganous complexes of EDTA have also been isolated in the form of copper and nickel bisbiguanidinium salts. The compounds are all stable and highly coloured.

Ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) has two basic nitrogen atoms and four carboxyl groups, and thus it can furnish six points of attachment to hexa-covalent metals like iron, chromium or cobalt, thereby making the metal co-ordinatively saturated as in (I). However, Schwarzenbach (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 839) has shown that this is not always the case and that it can sometimes function as a pentadentate unit, providing space for a foreign unfunctional ligand within the co-ordination sphere as in (II), in which case the complex metal ion becomes binegative in its electrical character. Schwarzenbach (*loc. cit.*) has been able to introduce Br^- and NO_2^- as foreign ligands in EDTA complexes with cobalt as the central atom. The normal EDTA complexes

[where $M = Fe, Cr$ or Co and $L = Br, NO_2, OH$ etc.]

of trivalent chromium and iron also can behave in a similar manner. This is apparent from the colour change which they undergo with increasing pH . Thus, chromium-EDTA complex is violet in acid medium, but dark blue in neutral or alkaline solution. The Fe-EDTA complex is lemon-yellow in acid or neutral solution, but dark red in alkaline medium. These have been attributed to the formation of hydroxo-complexes (Schwarzenbach, *loc. cit.*; Hamn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5670). But none of these hydroxo-complexes could be isolated due, no doubt, to the excessive solubility of the salts,

The nickel and copper complexes of EDTA have also been isolated only in the form of the free complex acids, $H_2 [Cu (C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8)]$ and $H_2 [Ni(C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8)]$ (Brintzinger and Hesse, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1942, 249, 113).

With a view to obtaining more informations regarding these hydroxo-EDTA complexes and to exploring the possibility of preparing crystalline salts of the copper- and nickel-EDTA complexes, the present investigation was undertaken. The Na salt of neither the violet acid $H [Cr (C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8)]$ nor of the blue acid $H_2 [Cr(C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8) (OH)]$ could be isolated. Even the heavy metal salts were much too soluble. It has, however, been possible to isolate the blue variety by precipitation with stable complex cations, such as copper and nickel bisbiguanidinium ions. The dark blue chromium complex was precipitated at p_H 7.6-7.8, whereas the dark red ferric complex at p_H 8.8. The nickel, copper and manganese complexes also have been isolated in the form of their copper and nickel bisbiguanidinium salts. It was further observed that hexammine cobaltic chloride or carbonatotetrammine cobaltic chloride were of little use for this purpose. This furnishes an evidence in support of the assumption that the solubility of a salt decreases with the increasing equalisation of the cationic and anionic volumes, particularly when they are large.

EXPERIMENTAL

bisBiguanidinium chloride of Cu and of Ni were prepared by following the method of Rây and Bagchi (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 618) and of Rây and Purkayastha (*ibid.*, 1941, 18, 218) respectively.

Copper bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-ethylenediaminetetra acetatochromiate.—Disodium salt of EDTA (~ 1.9 g., 1M) was dissolved in water (50 c.c.) and digested with an excess of freshly prepared chromic acetate, derived from the oxidation of freshly prepared chromous acetate. [Our earlier attempts to prepare the chromic complex by refluxing freshly prepared $Cr(OH)_3$ with EDTA led to difficulties in respect of removing the excess $Cr(OH)_3$, as it formed a colloidal suspension]. The resulting dark violet solution was filtered and the filtrate was treated with dilute NaOH or NH_4OH till the colour was distinctly dark blue (p_H 7.6-7.8). To this solution was added dropwise with constant stirring a concentrated solution of copper bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.9 g., 1M), when a violet-blue silky precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot water. The product was finally washed with alcohol and dried in air. {Found: Cu, 8.66; Cr, 7.00; H_2O (by loss at 120°), 14.51; C, 23.34; H, 4.69. $[Cu (C_2N_5H_7)_2] [Cr (C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8) (OH)] \cdot 6H_2O$ requires Cu, 8.69; Cr, 7.11; H_2O , 14.77; C, 22.99; H, 5.37 per cent}. The substance forms violet-blue soft needles, insoluble in cold water, but soluble in hot water.

The analyses may, however, appear to approach the formula $[Cu(C_2N_5H_7)_2] \cdot [Cr (C_{10}H_{12}N_2O_8)] Cl \cdot 6H_2O$, but we made sure that there was no chlorine, because, fusion with Na_2O_2 and Na_2CO_3 , followed by neutralisation and treatment with $AgNO_3$, did not show any silver chloride.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo ethylnediaminetetra-acetatochromiate.—The dark blue chromium complex, obtained as described above, was treated under stirring with a concentrated solution of nickel bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.8 g., 1M), when a blue-violet

silky crystalline precipitate separated from the solution. This was filtered, washed with water and purified by recrystallisation from hot water as in the previous case. {Found: Ni, 8.19; Cr, 7.23; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 12.76. [Ni (C₂N₅H₇)₂] [Cr (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)(OH)]. 5H₂O requires Ni, 8.28; Cr, 7.34; H₂O, 12.70 per cent}. The substance forms blue-violet soft needles, insoluble in cold water, but soluble in hot water. This compound also did not show the presence of any chlorine.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-ethylenediaminetetra-acetatoferrate.—Disodium salt of EDTA (1.9 g., 1 M) was dissolved in water (50 c.c.) and the solution was refluxed with an excess of freshly prepared Fe(OH)₃ for 3 hours. The resulting dark red solution (*p_H* 8.0) was filtered and then treated with dilute NaOH or NH₄OH till the *p_H* rose to 8.8. This solution was then treated dropwise with a concentrated solution of nickel bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.8 g., 1 M) with stirring, when an orange-yellow precipitate was formed. This was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol, and finally dried in air. This compound could not, however, be recrystallised, and showed slight traces of chlorine. {Found: Ni, 8.51; Fe 8.34; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 7.93; C, 24.88; H, 4.93. [Ni (C₂N₅H₇)₂] [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈) (OH)]. 3H₂O requires Ni, 8.68; Fe, 8.26; H₂O, 7.88; C, 24.85; H, 4.88 per cent}.

On the other hand, when the ferric complex was precipitated at *p_H* 7.0, the resulting product showed as much as 2.9% chlorine; [Ni (C₂N₅H₇)₂] [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈) Cl]. 3H₂O requires Cl, 5.11%. Thus at *p_H* 7.0, both the forms, H [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)] and H₂[Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)(OH)], remain in equilibrium in solution, and the biguanidinium salts of both the varieties, being insoluble, are precipitated together.

Copper bisBiguanidinium Hydroxo-ethylenediaminetetra-acetatoferrate.—The dark red EDTA-ferric complex, as described above, was treated with copper bisbiguanidinium chloride solution (1.9 g., 1 M) dropwise with stirring, when a reddish brown precipitate separated out. This was filtered, washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cu, 8.76; Fe, 7.66; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 12.66. [Cu (C₂N₅H₇)₂] [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈) (OH)]. 5H₂O requires Cu, 8.86; Fe, 7.79; H₂O, 12.55 per cent}. The compound could not be recrystallised, and it showed slight traces of chlorine.

When, however, the copper bisbiguanidinium chloride was added to the ferric complex at *p_H* 7.0, the product gave as much as 2.7% Cl, showing that both the forms, H [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)] and H₂ [Fe (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈) (OH)], remained in equilibrium.

Copper bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetonickeloate.—Disodium salt of EDTA (1.9 g., 1 M), dissolved in water, (50 c.c.), was refluxed with an excess of freshly prepared Ni(OH)₂ for 3 hours. The light blue neutral solution was filtered and the filtrate treated under stirring with copper bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.9 g., 1 M), when a rose-coloured precipitate separated out. This was filtered and recrystallised from hot water. The crystals were first washed with water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. They form beautiful rose-red needles, slightly soluble in cold water, but highly so in hot water. {Found: Cu, 8.51; Ni, 7.87; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 17.11; C, 23.24; H, 4.90. [Cu (C₂N₅H₇)₂] [Ni (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 7H₂O requires Cu, 8.60; Ni, 7.99; H₂O, 17.05; C, 22.74; H, 5.41 per cent}.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetonickeloate.—The pale blue solution of the EDTA-nickel complex was treated dropwise under stirring with a solution of nickel bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.8 g., 1 M). The resulting yellow precipitate was filtered, washed and recrystallised from hot water. The product was dried as usual. It forms pale yellow flakes, slightly soluble in cold water, but readily soluble in hot water. {Found: Ni, 16.09; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 16.79. [Ni (C₂N₂H₇)₂].[Ni (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 7H₂O requires Ni, 15.99; H₂O, 17.16 per cent}.

Copper bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetatecupriate.—Disodium salt of EDTA (1.9 g., 1 M), dissolved in water (50 c.c.), was digested on the water-bath with an excess of freshly prepared Cu(OH)₂ (washed nearly free from impurities) for 3 to 4 hours. The ϕ_{π} of the solution was adjusted to 7. This solution was then filtered and treated dropwise under stirring with an excess of copper bisbiguanidinium chloride solution. An ash-violet precipitate, contaminated with some copper bisbiguanidinium sulphate (from traces of sulphate retained by the copper hydroxide), separated from the solution. This was then dissolved in hot water and filtered to remove insoluble copper bisbiguanidinium sulphate. On cooling the filtrate, fine, needle-shaped, ash-violet crystals of the pure compound separated. These were dried as usual. {Found: Cu, 19.64; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 5.74; C, 25.89; H, 4.37. [Cu (C₂N₂H₇)₂].[Cu (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 2H₂O requires Cu, 19.45; H₂O, 5.57; C, 25.70; H, 4.58 per cent}.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetatecupriate.—When the deep blue solution of the EDTA-copper complex was treated with an excess of nickel bisbiguanidinium chloride solution, a rose-coloured precipitate, contaminated with small amounts of orange-yellow nickel bisbiguanidinium sulphate, separated out. This was filtered and purified by recrystallisation from hot water. {Found: Ni, 7.89; Cu, 8.65; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 17.08. [Ni (C₂N₂H₇)₂].[Cu (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 7H₂O requires Ni, 7.99; Cu, 8.60; H₂O, 17.05 per cent}. The substance forms light rose-coloured soft needles, slightly soluble in cold water, but readily in hot water.

Copper bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetato-manganese (II).—Disodium salt of EDTA (1.9 g., 1 M), dissolved in water (50 c.c.), was digested with an excess of freshly prepared MnCO₃. The pale yellowish pink solution was filtered and its ϕ_{π} adjusted to 7. This was then treated with copper bisbiguanidinium chloride solution (1.9 g.), when a rose-coloured crystalline precipitate was formed. The crystals were filtered, washed with water, and finally purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The substance forms rose-red shining crystals. {Found: Cu, 8.85; Mn, 7.61; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 15.26; C, 24.00; H, 5.29. [Cu (C₂N₂H₇)₂].[Mn (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 6H₂O requires Cu, 8.86; Mn, 7.66; H₂O, 15.06; C, 23.43; H 5.3 per cent}.

Nickel bisBiguanidinium Ethylenediaminetetra-acetato-manganese (II).—A solution of the manganous complex, obtained as described above, was treated dropwise under stirring with nickel bisbiguanidinium chloride (1.8 g., 1 M). A dirty yellow crystalline precipitate separated from the solution. This was filtered, washed and purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The product forms light yellow shining crystals. {Found: Ni, 8.55; Mn, 8.01; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 10.85. [Ni (C₂N₂H₇)₂].[Mn (C₁₀H₁₂N₂O₈)]. 4H₂O requires Ni, 8.68; Mn, 8.12; H₂O, 10.65 per cent}.

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-32.

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